

Limit of the Variation of the Relation between Intensity and Velocity of Photochemical Reactions.

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The problem of the relation between intensity and velocity of photochemical reactions is highly controversial and attempt has been made in this paper to throw some light on the problem from theoretical considerations.

It is well known that the velocity of a reaction is determined by the number of active molecules present in the reacting system, and that the photochemical acceleration consists in increasing this number of active molecules. Amount of photochemical acceleration at any time is, therefore, a factor which is dependent on the number of inactive molecules present at any instant. Greater the number of inactive molecules, greater is the probability of activation. According to Maxwell's distribution law, always a constant fraction of the total number is in the active state, when there is no removal by chemical change. The number of active molecules is thus always a constant fraction of the total number. The simplest assumption on this basis would, therefore, be that the same fraction of the inactive molecules is activated by equal increment in intensity.

With these assumptions the author (*U. P. Akad. Sci.*, 1933, 1, 54; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 199, 406) has deduced a theoretical expression for the relation between intensity and velocity of any photochemical reaction, from the view point of activation. If the intensity is varied in 'n' equal stages and A be the total number of molecules, x , the number of active molecules originally present before exposure, and y is the fraction of inactive molecules which get activated each time by exposure, then the photochemical acceleration in the first stage is proportional to $(A - x)y$, and in the n th stage is proportional to

$$(A - x) \{1 - (1 - y)^n\}.$$

It is evident from above that if the photochemical acceleration over the dark reaction is very small, y becomes very small. Moreover, y is a fraction and, therefore, less than unity. Hence the higher powers of y in the expansion of $(1-y)^n$ as squares, cubes, etc., may be neglected. The photochemical acceleration in the n th stage is, therefore, proportional to

$$(A-x) \{1 - (1-ny)\}$$

or

$$n(A-x)y.$$

Hence the photochemical acceleration in the n th stage or by increasing the intensity ' n ' fold is ' n ' times the acceleration in the first stage. That is, when the photochemical acceleration is small, the velocity is directly proportional to the intensity. However, when y is large, higher powers of y cannot be neglected, and hence the velocity—intensity relation is less than unity or approaches square root relationship.

Thus when the absorption of the radiation is high and the reaction is not markedly photochemical in nature and the velocity of the reaction in the dark is appreciable, direct proportionality is likely to be observed. On the other hand when the reaction is highly photochemical in nature and the velocity of the dark reaction is practically negligible, square root or less than the square root relationship will be expected.

The above theoretical expression not only explains the observed results but points out one very important fact, that the relation between intensity and velocity can never exceed unity for a truly photochemical reaction, and that in practically all the photochemical reactions, there must be a tendency to show a relationship which is less than the direct. Hence all the photochemical reactions so far studied may be divided only into two classes, *viz.*,

(i) The reactions showing a relationship between intensity and velocity which is less than the direct, the number of such reactions being large.

(ii) The reactions which obey direct relationship. The author's conclusions are clearly borne out by the numerous reactions investigated by various authors mentioned in the previous paper (*U. P. Akad. Sci.*, 1933, 1, 54). As the intensity is increased, the relation between intensity and velocity falls off gradually. In short, the reactions showing direct relationship are only few. The relation

between intensity and velocity in terms of a factor greater than the direct is not to be expected from the view advanced here.

It will be observed that even the ordinary consideration of activation fails to explain the existence of a relationship greater than the direct, which means that although the number of inactive molecules available for activation is actually decreasing with the increased intensity, yet the amount of activation or the number of molecules activated for the same increase in intensity is greater in the following stage, than in the preceding one. Since that is not possible, the existence of a relationship greater than the direct seems to be improbable.

Bhattacharya and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 493) have classified these reactions in the following three groups:

(1) Velocity tends to be directly proportional to the square of the incident radiation.

(2) Velocity tends to be proportional directly to intensity.

(3) Velocity tends to be proportional to the square root of the intensity.

The only peculiar example of the type in which more than direct relationship is observed, is found in the case of the photochemical reaction between hydrogen and chlorine, investigated by Baly and Barker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 653). Dhar and Bhattacharya (*loc. cit.*) have obtained similar relations in case of few photochemical reactions. It is interesting to note that special attempts were made by the authors to get such relationship by decreasing the photochemical acceleration with the help of such inhibitors as potassium bromide or potassium iodide.

An alternative suggestion to explain these few exceptions which cannot be explained merely on the principle of activation of the reacting molecules has been proposed. In author's opinion the part of the absorbed energy is used up in activating the molecules and the part is lost in destroying these inhibitors and hence the whole of the absorbed energy is not responsible for the reaction, and the proportionate loss of such energy, decreases with the increase in intensity. Hence the number of molecules actually activated in the next stage is always greater than the previous stage till whole of the inhibitor is destroyed. When there is no inhibitor left, no energy will be wasted in destroying it and the number of molecules activated will be directly proportional to the amount of energy absorbed,

hence the relationship which is greater than the direct will be no more observed. This suggestion of author actually explains the observed relations in case of hydrogen and chlorine reaction and the reactions with bromine and iodine investigated by Bhattacharya and Dhar (*loc.cit.*).

The reaction between hydrogen and chlorine is highly susceptible to impurities and the photochemical combination is retarded specially by oxygen. Thus the reacting mixture of Baly and Barker contained retarding substances, which are slowly destroyed by light. That is the amount of energy required to destroy this inhibitor went on proportionately decreasing with intensity and it appears therefore, that the reacting mixture of Baly and Barker shows a photochemical acceleration, which is greater than what is expected from the intensity. In this connection it will be of interest to note the following statement of Baly and Barker regarding the purity of their reaction mixture, "We found it very difficult to free the mixture completely from oxygen". This statement, therefore, seems to lend support to author's explanation.

Exactly similar explanation is applicable to the observations made by Bhattacharya and Dhar. Their experimental procedure shows that they have added an excess of potassium iodide or potassium bromide to suppress the photochemical acceleration. It is now an admitted fact that in bromine and iodine reactions in presence of potassium iodide or potassium bromide, KI_3 and KBr_3 molecules are formed, which act as internal filters, for the whole of the energy which is absorbed by the reactants, is not used up in activating the molecules. It is evident, therefore, that the author's explanation holds even in this case.

Thus all the photochemical reactions tend to show a relationship between intensity and velocity which is less than the direct.

Another important fact which is inherent in the expression is, that it is independent of the nature of the light source, but simply depends upon the amount of photochemical acceleration. It is usually observed that with the light of higher frequency or when the light quantum $h\nu$ is higher, the photochemical acceleration is higher, although according to Einstein's law, it should be the same. Hence, there should be greater chances of observing square root relationship in the region of higher frequency than in the region of lower frequency. The conclusion is fully supported by experiments.

Thus the present author has been able to explain the observed variation of velocity and intensity in case of photochemical reactions investigated by him and other numerous workers. The controversial problem in case of hydrogen, chlorine and other reactions has been satisfactorily explained.

SUMMARY.

1. It has been shown that the relation between intensity and velocity can show either direct relationship or a relationship which is less than the direct. From the view point of activation a relationship which is greater than the direct is improbable.

2. Only few reactions which are found to show apparently a relationship, greater than the direct, have been proved to be due to the presence of inhibitors which are destroyed by light, thereby the inhibition effect proportionately diminishing with intensity and apparently the velocity and intensity relation exceeds unity. Baly and Barker's observations regarding intensity and velocity of the photochemical reaction between hydrogen and chlorine and few of Bhattacharya and Dhar's reactions have been successfully explained.

3. It is shown that there are greater chances of observing square root relationship in a light of higher frequency than in a light of lower frequency, a fact borne out by experiments.

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